

MICROMECHANICAL MODELLING OF DENSELY PACKED SYNTACTIC FOAM COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper demonstrates a combined experimental-numerical method that enables accurate prediction of the elastic moduli and tensile failure strengths of syntactic foams. In general, for the systems studied, an increase in microsphere content resulted in an increase in the tensile modulus and a decrease in the tensile strength. The numerical method presented here is also capable of reproducing the experimental variability in tensile strength observed in the experimental data. At low particle loading ratios, the variance in observed experimental data can be almost entirely attributed to the distribution of interparticle distances between the microspheres, while at very high packing fractions, this is incapable of reproducing all of the experimentally observed variance in failure strengths.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite foams, known as syntactic foams, when filled with hollow microspheres are an efficient method to reduce weight in a high performance without significantly compromising on mechanical properties. This makes them a particularly suitable candidate material for applications in aerospace, marine, military and transport. In these applications, lightweight, load-bearing performance is crucial [1]. The porosity in an ideal syntactic foam is located entirely within the impermeable shell of the microsphere [2]. This makes these materials stronger and stiffer than conventional foams, and also limits moisture uptake, a key requirement for marine applications [3].

A micrograph of a densely paced syntactic foam is given in Figure 1. In this system, the microspheres are borosilicate glass, while the matrix is an epoxy resin. The foam can be seen to consist of three major phases, (1) the matrix, (2) the hollow glass spheres including both the external shell and the internal void and (3) some matrix porosity external to the microspheres. The external porosity arises as a consequence of the manufacturing process, where the matrix fails to fully fill the volume between the microspheres. However, it can be observed in this image, that the amount of matrix porosity is minimal. In this work, the effect of matrix porosity is neglected. There are then, three key regions within the syntactic foam composite that may cause failure, the microsphere, the matrix or the interface between the microsphere and the matrix. In this work, we demonstrate that by tailoring the structural and mechanical parameters of these regions, it is possible to optimise the properties of the syntactic foam for a particular application.

Experimental investigations are currently the best method of obtaining mechanical properties of syntactic foams. To date researchers have focused on measuring tensile properties [4,5], compressive properties [6-8] and flexural properties [9]. Predictive analytical methods have been adapted from those used to predict the properties of solid composite materials. These methods have largely focused on predicting the effective elastic properties of syntactic foams. Analytical predictions of strength, as in the case of solid composites are almost non-existent in the literature.

More recently, numerical methods have been used to model the behaviour of syntactic foams. A representative volume element (RVE) approach has gained favour to predict macroscopic material behaviour. Marur [10] and Antunes et al [11] used a unit cell approach, where the microspheres occupy fixed points in a regular lattice to predict the elastic properties of syntactic foams. Yu et al. [12] adopted a stochastic approach to predict the strength of syntactic foams. They used a random sequential adsorption process to generate random microstructures. They appear to among the first to recognise the

importance of geometric randomness when analysing the behaviour of syntactic foams. Segurado and Llorca [13] used a condensing process to obtain higher volume fractions of particles. The interaction between the glass microspheres and the matrix were assumed to obey a traction-separation law, although no physical justification or satisfactory discussion on the choice of parameters is given by the authors. Nian et al [14] reverted to a unit cell approach to model the modulus and strength of syntactic foams. They show that by altering the traction-separation law between the glass microspheres and the matrix, it is possible to fundamentally alter the failure process of the syntactic foam.

Figure 1: Micrograph of a fractured syntactic foam sample. The volume fraction of the glass microspheres is $\sim 64\%$.

2 COMPUTATIONAL MODEL

2.1 Model development

The random sequential adsorption (RSA) algorithm is widely used to generate random distributions of particles within an RVE [15]. In the first step of the algorithm, the position of the first particles is randomly selected, and the particle is seeded at this location within the RVE. Next, the position of the second particle is selected at randomly and a check is conducted to ensure that the second particle does not overlap with the first particle. If an overlap is detected, then the positioning of the second particle is reselected until no overlap is detected. All subsequent particles are then seeded within the microstructure if they satisfy the no-overlap condition with all existing particles in the RVE. The algorithm is elegant and simple, but it is not suitable for generating high volume fractions of particles. Indeed, several authors have reported a limit of approximately 30% volume fraction using this method [13, 16, 17].

In order to obtain packing fractions approaching the random close packing limit of 64%, the approach outlined by Lubachevsky and Stillinger [18] is adopted. This algorithm is based on a molecular dynamics approach. Firstly, the desired number of particles are placed within the RVE using the RSA algorithm. The individual particles are sized such that, in total, they occupy a very small volume in comparison to the overall space to be packed. A velocity vector, v_i , is assigned to each particle and a particle growth rate with respect to time is defined. The first time-step, dt , is calculated to coincide with the time of the first particle-particle collision. Subsequent time-steps are also calculated to coincide with the next collision. Collisions between particles are treated elastically. After each time-step, the energy in the system is renormalized to account for the growth of the particles. This has the effect of raising the temperature of the system, so that the particles do not slow down as they become more massive at later times. The treatment of particles which intersect the boundary of the RVE can be dealt with in two ways. The first option limits all particles to be contained entirely within the unit cell. Any particle intersecting the boundary of the RVE is reflected back into the RVE, bouncing off the wall. This is termed a ‘hard’

boundary condition and is preferable when non-physical stress concentration occurring at the interface between the microspheres, matrix and the boundary of the RVE cause premature failure of the model. The second option allows intersection of particles with the boundary but periodic boundary conditions on opposing faces. This means that when a particle or portion of a particle leave the RVE through a face it reappears at the opposing face, the particle or portion thereof reappears at the opposing face. This represents a ‘soft’ boundary condition and results in models that can be used to accurately explore maximum packing fractions of different families of particles. Exemplar finite element models with the ‘soft’ boundary condition are given in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The FEA model of the syntactic foam for (a) $v_f = 5\%$ and (b) $v_f = 60\%$. The matrix is coloured yellow whilst the microspheres are shown in grey

2.2 Material Properties

The material properties are given in Table 1. The matrix is modelled as a linear elastic material and the glass microspheres are IM30K hollow glass microspheres from 3M, with a mean diameter of $16 \mu\text{m}$ [19]. Although the IM30K microspheres display a lognormal distribution with respect to the particle diameter about, this was not explicitly modelled in the current work and all microspheres were assumed to have the mean diameter. Both matrix and microspheres were assumed to fail in a brittle manner, i.e. energy dissipation due to plasticity was assumed to contribute negligibly. This choice is supported by observations of the experimentally observed stress-strain curves, which all fail substantially before any large-scale yielding has taken place. The failure strength of the glass microspheres was estimated based on the reported crush strength of 193 MPa as per the data sheet [19]. This crush strength is defined as a pressure at which 90% of the microspheres have survived a hydrostatic compression test. By treating the microspheres as a thin-walled spherical pressure vessel, the maximum stress in the microsphere wall can then be estimated. Thus, a failure strength of 965 MPa was used as the failure strength of the microspheres. The fracture energy of glass was taken from the literature as 6 J/m^2 [20]. The fracture energy of the epoxy matrix was measured independently using single-notch bend tests. The second parameter required to construct a cohesive zone model for the epoxy matrix, the cohesive strength, is difficult to measure independently, but is expected to be of the order of the tensile yield strength.

3 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

A standard diglycidylether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) epoxy resin was used in the current work. This was cured at a stoichiometric ratio with iso-phorone diamine (IPD). Samples containing 10-30% microsphere volume fractions were manufactured by combining both the resin and curing agent with the required amount of microspheres under continuous stirring to ensure adequate dispersion of the microspheres. The use of IPD as a curing agent ensures a relatively rapid cure time, and the DGEBA resin is relatively viscous, thus limiting any buoyancy-induced agglomeration during cure. The mixture

of resin, curing agent and microspheres was degassed in a vacuum chamber to remove entrapped air bubbles and subsequently cast as a plaque in a silicone mould. High volume fraction plaques of material were manufactured using a proprietary process developed by FAC technology. Using this method, it is not possible to precisely control the volume fraction, but a volume fraction close to the theoretical maximum can be achieved.

Tensile tests were performed on the bulk epoxy resin as well as the glass microsphere modified syntactic foams to obtain the tensile modulus and the failure strength. The tests were conducted in accordance with ISO-527 [21]. Dumbbell shaped specimens with a gauge length of 30 mm were machined from 3 mm thick cast plaques of material. The tests were conducted under quasi-static conditions at a crosshead displacement rate of 1 mm/min. The sample strain was measured directly on the sample via a clip-on extensometer. Careful preparation of the edges of each tensile test specimen was undertaken. This involved polishing the edges to a smooth finish. This minimised the influence of the sample preparation on the failure strength. At least 20 specimens were tested in order to generate a large enough sample set that would be statistically representative of the behaviour of syntactic foam.

Properties	Matrix	Microspheres
<i>Young's modulus [GPa]</i>	3.17	70
<i>Poisson's ratio [-]</i>	0.35	0.2
<i>Failure strength [MPa]</i>	93.25	965
<i>Fracture energy [J/m²]</i>	22	6

Table 1: Material properties used in the current work.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Experimental results

The experimentally determined values of Young's modulus and fracture strength are given in Table 2. It can be seen that the Young's modulus increases with the addition of glass microspheres up to 40 vol.%. No further increase was observed with increased microsphere loading up to approx. 60 vol.%. Conversely, the fracture strength was observed to decrease with increased particle loading. It is also notable to observe that the standard deviation of the fracture strength for any composite material, given as the \pm value, also decreases with interparticle loading. This observation will be discussed further in conjunction with the numerical predictions.

v_f	E [GPa]	σ_f [MPa]
0	2.90±0.09	76.3±4.8
10	2.96±0.27	64.9±10.2
20	3.62±0.18	55.4±10.0
30	3.99±0.27	43.3±7.1
40	4.88±0.33	-
60	4.79±0.30	34.9±2.8

Table 2: Experimentally measured mechanical properties of different syntactic foam formulations.

4.2 Numerical Results: Calibration of the cohesive properties

The failure parameters required for each individual material component in the cohesive zone model are notoriously difficult to measure experimentally. Furthermore, while equivalent resin failure properties can be derived from macroscopic experiments, e.g. fracture toughness tests, differences in stress states at the microscopic level mean that these values may not be the correct properties to use at the microstructural scale. In this work, measured macroscopic properties were used as a starting point to conduct a calibration procedure. The calibration process follows a similar approach to that outlined by Carolan et al [22] for calculating cohesive zone properties from bluntly notched fracture toughness specimens. The process relies on recognising when adjusting either of the cohesive strength damage parameters, i.e. σ_m , the matrix strength or σ_{int} , the interface strength, the effect on the overall composite will be more or less pronounced depending on the volume fraction of microspheres. A similar argument can be made for the fracture energy of the matrix, G_m , and of the interface, G_{int} . Sensible upper and lower bounds are placed on these values and the calibration process is initiated over a subset of stochastic microstructures. The numerical results are then compared to the experimental results and the cohesive zone parameters are adjusted according to a set of predefined rules. Following the calibration process, the cohesive properties used in the numerical model for the interface between the resin and for the resin itself are chosen as: $\sigma_m = 102.8$ MPa, $\sigma_{int} = 23.2$ MPa, $G_m = 75$ J/m², $G_{int} = 40$ J/m².

4.3 Choice of initial cohesive stiffness at the interface

The choice of initial cohesive stiffness has long been a source of controversy in the finite element modelling community. Many studies report that it should be not too high, nor too low [23, 24]. The literature thus far can be summarised as: the value of cohesive stiffness should be large enough so as not to introduce artificial compliance into the system, but not so high as to promote numerical convergence problems. Such imprecise language is clearly unhelpful to defining the correct approach to choosing a penalty stiffness. Tan et al [25] report an experimental methodology to calculate the interface stiffness. However, this approach requires significant experimentation, including microscale digital image correlation to measure the parameters required for the model. A simpler approach has been proposed by Turon et al. [26]. In Turon's approach the cohesive stiffness, k_{coh} , is calculated as a function of the modulus of the matrix, E_m , and thickness of the cohesive element layer, t_{coh} .

$$k_{coh} = \alpha E_m / t_{coh} \quad (1)$$

where α is some parameter much greater than unity. Turon's approach has become ubiquitous in the literature, e.g. for modelling double cantilever beam specimens, but is only strictly correct for cases where the cohesive elements form an open surface, i.e. a surface with a boundary associated with it. In the case of a cohesive layer of elements wrapping around a closed surface such as a sphere, the choice of cohesive stiffness becomes critical. In the current work, the stiffness was matched to the elastic properties of the matrix via:

$$k_{coh} = E_m / t_{coh} \quad (2)$$

4.4 Tensile modulus

The numerically predicted tensile modulus is plotted in Figure 3 and compared to the experimentally obtained results. Reasonably good agreement between the numerical predictions and the experimentally measured values is observed. The numerical model is capable of picking up the plateau in tensile modulus recorded experimentally, although the numerical model tends to under predict the tensile modulus of highly filled syntactic foams.

Figure 3: Comparison of experimentally measured Young's modulus with numerical predictions made by the micro-mechanical model.

4.4 Tensile modulus

Figure 4 presents a comparison of the numerical predictions of failure strength made by the micromechanical model developed in this work with the experimentally observed failure strengths. Excellent agreement is achieved between the predictions and the measurements indicating that the developed model is capable of predicting the tensile failure response of polymer-matrix glass-microsphere syntactic foams across a wide range of particle loadings. This result is hardly surprising, since the cohesive parameters were calibrated to fit the experimental results and the general trend of decreasing strength with increased particle loading can also be recovered by simple analytical models such as Nicolais-Narkis [27] and Nielsen [28]. What is interesting however is that the numerical model reveals some interesting information about the experimentally observed scatter in failure strengths. The standard deviation, $SD(\sigma)$, of both the experimentally measured and numerically predicted failure strength as a function of particle volume fraction is plotted in Figure 5. It can be clearly observed that in both the experimental measurements and the numerical model, the standard deviation of the strength decreases with increasing volume fraction of microspheres. Furthermore, remarkable agreement in the degree of scatter is obtained when comparing experiment and predictions. This lends the presented numerical model a predictive power hitherto unreported in the literature, an ability to describe scatter in strength experiments.

Figure 4: Comparison of experimentally measured failure strength with the numerical predictions made by the micromechanical model.

Figure 5: Comparison of the experimentally measured scatter in fracture strength data with the numerical predictions made by the micromechanical model.

4.7 Weibull analysis

The strength measurements and predictions of macroscopically identical syntactic foam specimen exhibited large degrees of scatter in the measured data. Consequently, the strength is poorly defined using an approach based solely on the considering mean values and standard deviation. A more informative approach is to use Weibull statistics to quantitatively characterise the scatter in the strength data [29]. The Weibull distribution has been used extensively in the ceramics community to accurately describe the strength distribution of brittle materials [30, 31]. The cumulative failure probability for the three parameter model is given as:

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp(-[\sigma/\sigma_0]^m + [\sigma_p/\sigma_0]^m) \quad (1)$$

where m is the Weibull modulus, σ_0 is the characteristic strength and σ_p is the proof strength below which failure will not occur.

A comparison of the Weibull distribution for the low volume fraction, 10% and the high volume fraction, 55%-60% is presented in Figure 6. A number of observations may be made from a close inspection of this data. Firstly, there is excellent agreement between the experimental measurements and the numerical prediction for the stochastic models with a microsphere volume fraction of 10%. Both experimental results and numerical predictions exhibit an upper and lower tail to the distribution. The

existence of the lower tail indicates the existence of a lower bound, or proof stress, below which failure will not occur. Conversely, the presence of an upper tail indicates that there also exists an upper bound or maximum strength which can be achieved in the syntactic foam. The excellent agreement between experiment and prediction implies the variation in the underlying microstructure is primarily responsible for the observed variation in fracture strengths experimentally as this is the only parameter which varies between each instantiation of the numerical model at this volume fraction.

In the case of highly filled syntactic foams, the correlation between experiment and prediction is not as good. The numerical model predictions show a tighter distribution than the experimental observations. Nevertheless, the essential features of the three parameter Weibull distribution are still captured. In a highly filled syntactic foam, there cannot be much variation in microstructure in terms of the distance between particles. Indeed, at the random close packing limit, all microspheres will be touching their nearest neighbours by definition. Thus the geometric variation in the microstructure alone is insufficient to explain the observed variance in fracture strength.

Figure 6: Weibull distribution of experimental measurements and numerical predictions for syntactic foams with 10 vol.% (squares) and 55-60 vol.% (circles).

4.7 Parametric study

Having confirmed the potential usefulness of the model in predicting tensile failure of syntactic foam, a parametric study was conducted. This individually isolated the influence of matrix cohesive strength, σ_m , and interfacial cohesive strength, σ_{int} , on the failure behaviour of the syntactic foam. For each volume fraction, the cohesive strength of the matrix, σ_m , was increased and decreased by 50%, i.e. $1.5\sigma_m$ and $0.67\sigma_m$. The cohesive strength at the interface, σ_{int} , was kept constant. The results of this study are presented in Figure 7. It can be seen that by changing the value of large differences in the fracture strength of the syntactic foam can be realized at low microsphere loading, while it has a relatively insignificant impact on the fracture strength of a heavily filled syntactic foam.

Similarly, the cohesive strength of the interface, σ_{int} , was alternately increased and decreased by 50%. In practice, this can be realized by suitable functionalisation of the glass microspheres, e.g. silanisation. The results of this are presented in Figure 8. Some differences in the fracture strength of the syntactic foam composite are realized at low volume fraction, these are not as significant as in the case presented in Figure 6. Significant improvements or dis-improvements can be made for highly filled syntactic foams by adjusting the interfacial cohesive strength.

Figure 7: Effect of varying matrix cohesive strength, σ_m , on failure response of syntactic foam composites.

Figure 7: Effect of varying matrix cohesive strength, σ_{int} , on failure response of syntactic foam composites.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A numerical model for predicting the mechanical properties of syntactic foam has been developed. The model is capable of predicting the failure of syntactic foams across a wide range of microsphere loadings. Moreover, the model has also demonstrated the capability to predict the expected variance in the tensile fracture strength of the syntactic foam. The variation in fracture strength has been linked to the randomness of the underlying microstructural geometry. The existence of an upper and lower bound to the variation in fracture strength has been shown experimentally and predicted numerically. A parametric study has indicated that the fracture strength of highly filled syntactic foam can be improved by suitable functionalisation of the microsphere surface. The results presented in this work highlight the importance of considering randomness and microstructural variation when studying the failure of syntactic foam composites, or particulate composites in general. The model presented can be used to design stronger syntactic foams composites and allow for more robust design of components containing syntactic foam composites.

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